

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Sl. no.	Compd./Colour	Mol. Cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2}$) in				$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu_{\text{Mo-Cl}}$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (cm^{-1})	Magnetic moments (B. M.)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
		Methanol	DMF	DMSO						
1.	[(FALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄] Yellow	90	80	55	1596		805	1.66	285	
2.	[(IALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄] Brownish yellow	64	87	48	1566		790	1.63	325	
3.	[(MSALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄] Brownish black	76	75	34	1550		774	1.64	335	
4.	[(M'SALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄] Orange	88	70	48	1535		780	1.69	295	
5.	[(BSALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄] Black	60	84	39	1561		775	1.62	288	
6.	[(FALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂] Brown	195	150	55	1570		790	5.84	280	
7.	[(IALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂] Blackish brown	190	145	57	1560		794	5.76	320	
8.	[(MSALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂] Yellow	185	130	48	1535		770	5.83	330	
9.	[(M'SALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂] Orange	210	155	52	1565		810	5.89	295	
10.	[(BSALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂] Black-brown	192	158	56	1569		805	5.90	270	
		<u>C₆H₅NO₂</u>	<u>CH₃CN</u>	<u>CH₃OH</u>	<u>DMF</u>					
11.	[(FALT).MoOCl ₂] Brownish black	2.1	5.2	23.6	18.4	1580	275	785	1.67	285
12.	[(IALT).MoOCl ₂] Yellow	0.8	11.6	15.6	17.8	1550	365	780	1.63	320
13.	[(MSALT).MoOCl ₂] Yellowish orange	3.1	2.7	8.3	22.4	1540	350	760	1.64	325
14.	[(M'SALT).MoOCl ₂] Brown	1.6	5.8	10.5	16.6	1562	310	795	1.70	290
15.	[(BSALT).MoOCl ₂] Yellowish orange	1.9	10.8	12.4	15.8	1565	295	785	1.62	295

electronic spectral of the manganese(II) complexes exhibit weak bands in the regions of 17000–18500, 20700–22200, 24900–26100, 27000–28000 and 29000 cm^{-1} . The three low energy bands arising from the sextet quartet $t_{2g}^3 e_g^2$ configuration have been assigned⁶ to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ (17000–18500 cm^{-1}), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}(G)$ (20700–22200 cm^{-1}) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ (24900–26100 cm^{-1}). The other bands around 27500 and 29000 cm^{-1} are assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}(D)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(D)$ respectively, in an octahedral. The lower energy bands, assigned to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^4T_{2g}(G) \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$, were used to calculate the higher energy bands and the values thus obtained are quite close to those observed.

The complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and manganese(II) were subjected to thermogravimetric analysis and the thermogram has helped in ascertaining the presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes as well as thermal stability of the complexes. These complexes has no coordinated water molecules.

The IR spectra of ligands FAL, IAL, MSAL, M'SAL, BSAL show two important peaks at 1615 and 1585 cm^{-1} which were shifted to 1535–1596 and 760–810 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the complexes indicating coordination occurs

through N atoms of azomethine ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$)⁷ and S atoms of thio groups ($\nu_{\text{C=S}}$) in all complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and manganese(II) a peak appeared at 730–915 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules. In all complexes of oxomolybdenum(V) a sharp peak appeared at 275–365 cm^{-1} showed the coordination occurred through chlorine atom⁸. A very strong band occurring at 920–940 cm^{-1} in the present oxo Mo^V complexes can be attributed to $\nu(\text{Mo=O})$ ⁹.

The ESR spectrum of the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes which were recorded in polycrystalline form at room temperature, exhibited a single line only. The ESR parameters were found to be $g_{\parallel} = 1.9932$, $g_{\perp} = 1.958$ and $g_{av} = 1.9697$. The g_{av} value indicates that the pentavalent Mo in the complex is monomeric¹⁰. The spectra of manganese(II) complexes consist of a single broad peak in each case. For the present complexes the g lies in the range 2.053–2.091 indicating a tetra coordinated state for these complexes. Oxovanadium(IV) complexes exhibit no hyperfine structure characteristic to vanadyl ion. The vanadyl ion exhibiting an isotropic single line ESR spectrum with ' g ' value of 2.023 G which is high in comparison either with free-electron value or with the ' g ' value observable (~ 1.985 G) in any ligand environment. The higher ' g ' value is attributable to strong σ donation from the equatorially bounded ligands¹¹.

Table 2. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Metal % (Found/calcd.)	% of Carbon (Found/calcd.)	% of Hydrogen (Found/calcd.)	% of Nitrogen (Found/calcd.)	% of Sulphur (Found/calcd.)	% of Chlorine (Found/calcd.)
1.	[(FALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄]	8.2491 (7.3593)	39.6344 (38.0952)	–	13.2131 (12.1212)	14.9412 (13.8528)	–
2.	[(IALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄]	6.5349 (5.7367)	51.9378 (51.2936)	–	16.2112 (15.7483)	11.8366 (10.7987)	–
3.	[(MSALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄]	6.1263 (5.9788)	48.1921 (47.8311)	–	10.0343 (9.8475)	12.4343 (11.2543)	–
4.	[(M'SALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄]	6.2316 (5.9788)	–	–	10.9464 (8.8143)	12.1667 (10.0734)	–
5.	[(BSALT).2H ₂ O.VOSO ₄]	6.4316 (5.3515)	–	–	9.3143 (9.8475)	11.1124 (11.2543)	–
6.	[(FALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂]	7.9212 (8.3841)	41.3261 (40.2439)	4.1204 (3.3536)	13.5403 (12.8084)	10.1326 (9.7560)	8.5038 (8.875)
7.	[(IALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂]	5.9123 (6.4553)	54.3124 (53.5211)	4.3218 (3.9906)	10.5634 (9.8591)	8.6346 (7.5117)	7.9936 (8.3333)
8.	[(MSALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂]	–	51.2021 (50.000)	5.1134 (4.6569)	11.1034 (10.2941)	8.1291 (7.8431)	8.0096 (8.70098)
9.	[(M'SALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂]	–	51.3602 (50.000)	5.1052 (4.6569)	9.9836 (10.2941)	8.2213 (7.8431)	8.698712 (8.70098)
10.	[(BSALT).2H ₂ O.MnCl ₂]	–	40.4310 (39.3013)	3.7321 (2.8384)	10.2643 (9.1703)	7.4326 (6.9868)	7.992111 (7.75109)
11.	[(FALT).MoOCl ₂]	13.6137 (14.1802)	39.6683 (38.9956)	3.9120 (2.6588)	13.0312 (12.4077)	8.7381 (9.4535)	8.00987 (8.6479)
12.	[(IALT).MoOCl ₂]	11.1678 (10.9966)	53.0136 (52.2337)	4.4246 (3.1426)	16.0137 (16.0367)	8.4142 (7.3310)	7.99908 (8.13287)
13.	[(MSALT).MoOCl ₂]	10.6482 (11.4695)	49.5340 (48.7455)	5.1343 (4.0621)	11.1673 (10.0358)	8.3146 (7.6464)	8.569870 (8.48267)
14.	[(M'SALT).MoOCl ₂]	10.9682 (11.4695)	39.6321 (48.7455)	5.0349 (4.0621)	11.1321 (10.0358)	8.2137 (7.6464)	8.669871 (8.48264)
15.	[(BSALT).MoOCl ₂]	11.1233 (10.2455)	39.1634 (38.425)	3.1688 (2.3479)	9.7314 (8.9648)	7.1346 (6.8303)	7.069887 (7.57737)

On the basis of available evidences, octahedral geometry may be suggested for all oxovanadium(IV) and manganese(II) complexes and distorted octahedral (distortion due to Mo=O bond) geometry is suggested for all oxomolybdenum(V) complexes. The structure of the complexes is given below, where 'M' is the metal ion, X⁻ is Cl⁻ or 1/2 SO₄²⁻ and L is H₂O or Cl⁻. In the case of manganese(II) complex there is no coordinated 'O' to metal and the complex is six coordinated.

Thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones possess N–C=S group which is an essential structural feature responsible for various biocidal properties¹². The oxovanadium(IV) complexes were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity and the inhibition zone diameter in mm are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

The antibacterial activity of Mn^{II} complexes was carried out against 24 h cultures of four selected bacteria. The bacterial activity was performed by cup-plate technique. The agar cups were made by preceded (12 ml) melted agar medium at 50 °C by boring 1 cm thick broth culture on a plate by 10 mm cork borer. Two drops of the melted agar were

pipetted in to it, incubated for 24 h and zone of inhibition observed results obtained are presented in Table 5.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity at 3 µg/disc (zone formation in mm)

Compd.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. licheniformes</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. bravis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>K. aeruginosa</i>
1	10	8	10	7	7	nil	12
2	11	7	11	7	7	nil	10
3	10	8	10	6	7	nil	9
4	10	8	10	7	6	nil	11
5	10	7	11	7	7	nil	12

Table 4. Response of the test compound (at 1 mg/ml) against fungi

Compd.	<i>Penicillin species</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Rhizopus species</i>	<i>Phytothora infestana</i>	<i>Aspergillus species</i>	<i>Saccharo myces</i>
1	–	–	–	+/-	+	–
2	–	–	–	+/-	+	–
3	–	–	–	+/-	+	–
4	–	–	–	+/-	+	–
5	–	–	–	–	+	–

(+) Not active, (–) active, (+/-) moderately active.

Table 5. Antibacterial screening in DMF

Compd	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)			
	<i>S aureus</i>	<i>E coli</i>	<i>B subtilis</i>	<i>S pyrogens</i>
6	10	8.0	11.4	9.8
7	9.2	7.0	10.1	9.6
8	9.6	9.2	10.7	9.1
9	9.5	9.4	10.6	9.4
10	10.0	8.2	11.2	9.5

The fungicidal activities of the complexes were evaluated by testing them against different species at different concentrations. The results of fungicidal screening it recorded in Table 6.

Table 6 Fungicidal screening data

Average % inhibition of spore germination after 72 h

Compd	<i>Alternaria alternata</i> (conc in ppm)			<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (conc in ppm)		
	100	500	1000	100	500	1000
6	52	57	62	49	47	57
7	49	52	60	41	50	56
8	50	56	61	43	50	54
9	51	53	62	46	49	52
10	49	57	60	42	51	53

Experimental

All the complexes used were A R. grade (B.D.H., Koch Light and Fluka).

Preparation of Schiff bases :

The Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of respective aldehyde with thiosemicarbazide. The amino compound was dissolved in ethanol and refluxed for about half an hour. The requisite amount of the respective aldehyde was then added to the flask. The mixture was then refluxed for about six hours. The reaction mixture was kept for 24 h. The crystals of the ligand were obtained, which were purified by recrystallisation

Preparation of metal complexes :

Preparation of oxovanadium(IV) and manganese(II) complexes : V^{IV} and Mn^{II} complexes were synthesised by the addition of salt solution in methanol to the solution of ligand in DMSO/THF. The ppt. thus obtained was washed with DMSO/THF and dried over fused $CaCl_2$.

Preparation of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes : A methanolic solution of $MoCl_5$ (2 mmol) was added in small quantities with stirring to a hot solution of the ligand (2 mmol) in methanol. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 6 with NaOAc/HOAc buffer and stirring continued for 10–15 min. The solid complex that separated was washed with aqueous methanol and dried over, P_4O_{10} in vacuum.

References

- 1 M M Mostafa, A A El-Asmy and K M Ibrahim, *Transition Met Chem*, 1983, 8, 54, N P Bow hoi, T B Voc and N D Zuong, *Bull Soc Chim Fr*, 1955, 694, N Orlava, V A Akssnova, D A Solidovkin, N S Bocdanova and G N Perkin, *Russ Pharm Toxicol*, 1968, 348, F P Dwyer, F Mayhew, F M F Roe and A Shulman, *Br J Cancer*, 1965, 19, 195
- 2 J P Scovill, D L Klayman and C F Franchino, *J Med Chem*, 1982, 25, 1261
- 3 J A Walmsley and S V Tyree, *Inorg Chem*, 1993, 2, 312, W J Geary, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1971, 7, 81
- 4 A G Sykes, "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", ed G Wilkinson, Pergamon, New York, 1987, 1229, B N Figgis and R S Nyholm, *J Chem Soc*, 1958, 4190, A Syamal and S Ahmed, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1991, 30, 640
- 5 C J Ballhausen and A B Gray, *Inorg Chem*, 1962, 1, 111
- 6 C J Ballhausen and H B Gray, "Molecular Orbital Theory", Benjamin, New York, 1965, A B P Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, 292
- 7 S K Sahni, M P Swami, D P Joshi and V B Rana, "Proceedings of the Convention of Chemists", Bangalore, 1976, 30, B Singh, Lakshmi and U Agarwala, *Inorg Chem*, 1969, 8, 2341, U Agarwala and B J Singh, *Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1969, 31, 2575, J S Dwivedi and U Agarwala, *Indian J Chem*, 1972, 10, 652, 657
- 8 K Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963
- 9 E I Steifel, *Prog Inorg Chem*, 1977, 22, 1, D J A Raj, K S Nagaraja and M R Udupa, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1985, 24, 869, P C H Mitchell, *Quart Rev*, 1996, 20, 103
- 10 W Gordey, "Theory and Applications of Electron Spin Resonance", John Wiley, New York, 1980, A Abragam and B Bleaney, "Electron Paramagnetic Resonance of Transition Ions", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1970
- 11 B Venugopalan, S Sureshi, P J De Souza and N Chatterjee, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1991, 30, 777

Verma *et al.* : Oxovanadium(IV), oxomolybdenum(V) and manganese(II) complexes of Schiff bases *etc.*

12. R. S. Varma, K. C. Gupta and V. S. Mishra, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1964, **4**, 63; V. K. Mishra and S. C. Bahel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **60**, 867; H. Singh and L. D. S. Yadav, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1976, **40**, 759; R. B. Pathak and S. C. Bahel, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Ageriles*, 1984, **12**; G. D. Throm and R. S. Ludwig, "The Dithiocarbamates and Related Compounds", Elsevier, New York, 1952; D. S. Deshpande, *Chem. Abst.*, 1981, **94**, 655568; C. P. Prabhakaran and M. L. Hari Kumaran Nair, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 7.